

**SPATIAL ASSESSMENT OF MIGRATION AND ITS DRIVING FORCE IN
ALIMOSHO LOCAL GOVERNMENT, LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Migration has remained a fundamental aspect of human existence, and has a significant influence on the pattern of population and urban development globally. However, there is limited understanding of how different migration trends collectively affect population composition and dynamics in rapidly growing megacities like Lagos, Nigeria. This study examines the spatial assessment of migration and its driving forces in Alimosho Local Government Area, Lagos State, with the aim of analyzing the impact of internal and international migration on the area's demographic structure. The specific objectives were to determine population composition of migration, identify spatial patterns and characteristics of migration, examine driving factors of migration, assess challenges facing migrants, and proffer means of improving migrants' livelihood in the study area.

Migration theories, such as Lee's Theory of Migration and Ravenstein's Law of Migration provided the theoretical framework for the study. The study employed a survey design using both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through structured questionnaires administered to 99 household heads across 11 wards in Alimosho LGA using stratified sampling technique. The 2024 projected population of 2,094,524 was used as the study population, with migrants representing 36% of total households based on International Organization for Migration statistics. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Multiple Linear Regression.

Key findings reveal a predominantly female migrant population (56.6%) with high educational attainment (43.4% tertiary education). Most migrants (40.4%) were aged 36-45 years, married (46.5%), and self-employed (50.5%). Urban-to-urban migration dominated (80.8%) over rural-to-urban migration (19.2%), with Ogun State being the primary source (35.4%). Job opportunities emerged as the strongest pull factor while unemployment was the primary push

factor. The ANOVA revealed significant association between factors attracting migrants ($F=13.176$, $p<0.001$), but no significant association between push factors ($F=2.640$, $p=0.053$). Multiple regression showed limited explanatory power ($R^2=0.135$) for the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics and challenges faced. Limited access to education was the most prevalent challenge (58.6%), followed by lack of employment opportunities (35.4%).

Recommendations include prioritizing diverse employment creation, developing affordable housing schemes through public-private partnerships, expanding educational infrastructure and implementing scholarship programs for migrant children, enhancing healthcare facilities in migrant-dense areas, and establishing financial support initiatives including microfinance programs and cooperative societies to improve migrants' livelihoods and maximize the benefits of migration for urban development.

Keywords: Migration patterns, urban-to-urban migration, population dynamics, Alimosho Local Government, Lagos State, demographic composition, pull factors, push factors.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The phenomenon of migration has remained part and parcel of the existence of mankind since the dawn of history, as humans have always involved themselves in movement activities. Migration, both internal and international, is a common feature of both developing and developed countries. Internal migration here refers to the movement of people within their country of origin (in-migration and out-migration), which could be due to various social, economic and political factors. Poulain and Perrin (2023) defined international migration as “the movement of people out of their home country (emigration) into another country (immigration)”. Migration is an intrinsic part of human existence, with a long history. However, its pattern has significantly changed over time, from the search for space, especially in the middle ages, to that of congestion in megacities (rural-urban migration) in the contemporary age. This is especially so in the last millennium. Three-fifths of the world’s population is expected to live in urban areas in 2030 (Nwodom et al., 2017).

Migration has the potential to bring about rapid changes in population size, composition, and distribution, particularly at the local level. The global COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated this to dramatic effect when international border closures impacted the global migration flows (González-Leonardo et al., 2023). The last decade has seen significant advances, with estimates of migration stocks and bilateral migration flows produced (Abel and Cohen, 2019). New data have provided surprising insights into the trends and patterns of both internal and international migration. The most noteworthy of these has been the relative stability in the volume and intensity of global migration flows (Abel and Sander 2014; De Haas et al. 2019). It is, therefore,

important to understand the complex relationship between migration and population dynamics for proper and effective planning and sustainable development.

Over the years, there have been significant migration in Nigeria, both internally and in the international scene. Some of the factors that contribute to this rural-urban migration include lack of employment opportunities, lack of infrastructural facilities, educational institution, etc. (Nweke, 2018). International migration is largely motivated by economic forces, although demographic, environmental, policy, and political factors also play a role (Sander et al., 2013). The volume of migration reflects conditions at the source and destination, mediated by distance-cost, and is expected to change over time as countries develop. Migration patterns are processes have various effects on the country's changing demographics. They shape family structures and fertility rates, and have a large influence on population distribution, cultural diversity, the distribution and demand for health care, and the composition of labour force. In Nigeria, the population of urban areas and cities such as Lagos, Kano, Abuja, etc have grown at a fast rate, leading to a strain of public services and infrastructures like road. On the other hand, rural areas have experienced depopulation and loss of manpower which affects the local economy and agricultural productivity. (Adebayo, 2023).

Demographic changes resulting from migration patterns are often seen in urbanization processes. Cities experience population growth and a change in their age structure as people move from rural to urban areas in search of greener pastures and improved living conditions, (Kasarda & Crenshaw, 2016). This lead to increased rate of urbanization and contribute to the diversity of culture in a region, due to movement of people from diverse cultural backgrounds. This demographic diversity have both positive and negative effects, evident on social cohesion, economy and on policy formulation. The family sizes and childbearing habits may also vary

from that of the host population. This may lead to changes in the regions fertility rate and may have severe consequences on population growth and age distribution (IOM, 2015).

1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The city of Lagos has long been a destination for local migrants from within Nigeria, as well as from other countries around the world, leading to a rapid growth in the population of the city. The main driver of this population increase continues to be internal migration from other Nigerian states, but the city also draws in international migrants from the immediate neighbouring West African countries and beyond. At the same time, Lagos acts as a major departure point for Nigerians who aim to seek greener pastures overseas, making the city a very important environment for migrants.

The Lagos State Government, in a local report, said migration was a major factor in the city's population expansion, which increased from about 11.2 million in 2011 to an estimated 26 million in 2022. According to the Lagos State Bureau of Statistics, more than 60% of the city's inhabitants are migrants from other Nigerian States or adjacent countries. This swift increase in population has turned the city into one of the fastest-growing megacities in the world, with obvious effects on its urban development, socioeconomic environment, and demographic makeup. While this transformation is crucial, there is a notable lack of understanding regarding how different migration trends collectively affects the population composition and dynamics in Lagos. This absence of this understanding presents serious challenges for the city to effectively manage the effects on policy development and urban planning. It also hinders the city's capacity to effectively tackle the pressures on urban infrastructure and public services.

Thus, there is a pressing need for a thorough investigation of how both national and international migration trends influence the population dynamics of Lagos. Such investigation

is necessary for guiding evidence-based policymaking and creating sustainable urban planning strategies that can accommodate, and more importantly capitalize on, the city's rapid growth driven by migration. This study will critically examine how migration patterns influence population dynamics in the city of Lagos, Nigeria, and assist to fill this gap. The study, therefore aims to deliver a curtailed investigation of how both internal and international migration alters the demographic composition of Lagos.

1.3 RESEARCH GAP

The research gap in this study centers on the insufficient exploration of how migration patterns influence population dynamics in Lagos, Nigeria. While existing literature addresses migration broadly, there is a lack of specific, localized studies that examine the ways internal and international migration impact Lagos's demographic structure, infrastructure, and public services. Although general insights into migration factors are available, they often fail to detail the social, economic, and environmental repercussions of migration on rapidly urbanizing cities like Lagos. Furthermore, while traditional push-pull factors such as economic hardship and political instability have been well-documented, contemporary influences like climate change and environmental degradation are not adequately explored. This oversight leaves a significant gap regarding how these newer drivers of migration affect the urban population of Lagos. Additionally, existing studies often focus on the general impacts of migration on urban growth but neglect to analyze the challenges faced by migrants to Lagos.

This study aims to address these gaps by providing a focused analysis of Lagos, investigating contemporary migration patterns and their comprehensive impact on the city's demographic trends, socioeconomic development, and infrastructure.

1.4 JUSTIFICATION OF STUDY

This study on the influence of migration on the population of Lagos provides an understanding of how migration affects and shape one of the world's fastest-growing megacities. This research will help policymakers develop effective strategies to manage urban growth and public service provision in the country. The findings of this study will help Government and her Agencies in formulating policies that will help to tackle the negative impacts of migration. As Lagos continues to experience a rapid and migration-driven growth, this study will provide urban planners with essential insights to anticipate and plan for future challenges and opportunities. The study will shed light on how migration patterns influence Lagos' population distribution, and provide recommendations for harnessing the benefits of migration while also addressing related challenges. Additionally, this study will provide insights to the factors influencing the migration of people, both from rural areas and other urban centres, into Lagos.

The study will make a significant contribution to literature on urban population, migration studies, and growth of urban centres in developing nations. The study will lay a foundation for further research in other growing cities – both in Nigeria and beyond - contributing to the understanding of how migration influence urban growth. Since the focus of this research is on sustainable cities, it aligns with UN Sustainable Development Goals and will help to achieve this objective in an African city.

In conclusion, this study addresses current knowledge gaps and is crucial for the sustainable development of Lagos, it contributes to broader academic and global development objectives.

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How does migration affect population composition in Alimosho Local Government Area?
2. What is the spatial patterns and characteristics of migration in the study area?
3. What are the driving factors affecting migration in the study area?

4. What challenges do migrants face in the study area?

1.6 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The aim of this research is to analyze the impact of internal and international migration on Lagos's demographic structure.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the population composition of the migration in Alimosho Local Government Area.
2. Identify the spatial pattern and characteristics of migration in the study area.
3. Examine the driving factors of migration in the study area.
4. Examine the challenges facing migrants in the study.
5. Proffer means of improving livelihood of migrants in the study area.

1.6.1 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H01: There is no significant association between the factors attracting migrants to Alimosho Local Government Areas.

H02: There is no significant association between the factors pushing migrants out of their source regions.

H03: There is no significant relationship between the level of challenge faced by the migrants and their socioeconomic characteristics.

1.7 STUDY AREA: Lagos State

Lagos State was established on 27th of May, 1967 by virtue of States (Creation and Transitional Provisions) Decree No. 14 of 1967 which restructured Nigeria's Federation into 12 States. Lagos Municipality was, before this time, administered as a Federal Territory by the Federal

Government through the Federal Ministry of Lagos Affairs as the regional authority, while the City of Lagos was governed Lagos City Council. In the same vein, the Metropolitan areas (Colony Province) of Ikeja, Mushin, Ojo, Ikorodu, Epe, Agege and Badagry were administered by the Western Region Government. Lagos State began as an administrative entity on April 11, 1968 with Lagos Island serving as both the State and Federal Capital. However, with the creation of the Federal Capital Territory of Abuja in 1976, Lagos Island ceased to be the capital of the State, as this was moved to Ikeja. Similarly, with the formal relocation of the seat of the Federal Government to Abuja on 12th December, 1991, Lagos ceased to be political capital of Nigeria. Nevertheless, she continues to maintain her status as the economic and commercial capital of the country.

Location/Extent

Lagos State is located in the South–Western part of Nigeria, on the narrow plain of the Bight of Benin. It lies approximately on longitude **20 42'E and 32 2'E** respectively, and between latitude **60 22'N and 60 2'N**. It is bounded in the North and East by Ogun State of Nigeria, in the West by Republic of Benin, and stretches over 180 kilometers along the Guinea Coast of the Bight of Benin on the Atlantic Ocean. The political jurisdiction and geographical extent of the State spreads across the city of Lagos and the four administrative divisions of Ikeja, Ikorodu, Badagry and Epe collectively referred to as IBILE and occupying an area of 358,862 hectares or 3,577 sq. km. This represents 0.4% of Nigeria's territorial land mass of 923,773 sq. km.

Relief

Lagos State's dominant vegetation is the swamp forest of the fresh water and mangrove swamp forests, both of which are influenced by the double rainfall pattern of the state, hence making the environment a wetland region. Generally, the State experiences two climatic seasons: The Dry (November-March) and Wet (April-October) seasons. The drainage system of Lagos State

consists of a maze of lagoons and waterways, which covers about 22% or 787 sq. km. [75.755 hectares] of the State's total land mass. The major water bodies are the Lagos and Lekki Lagoons, Yewa, Ogun, Oshun, and Kweme Rivers. Others are Ologe Lagoon, Kuramo Waters, and Badagry, Five Cowries and Omu Creeks respectively.

Demography

Lagos State is the smallest state in Nigeria yet, it has the highest urban population, or 27.4 % of the national estimate [UN-Habitat]. Lagos State was enumerated to have a population of 9,013,534, according to the 2006 National Census, in relation to the National count of 140,003,542. However, the UN-Habitat and international development agencies' estimate that Lagos State has about 24.6 million inhabitants in 2015. Of this, Metropolitan Lagos accounts for over 85% on an area that is 37% of the land area of the State. Lagos population is growing 10 times faster than that of New York and Los Angeles, and more than the population of 32 African nations combined, the State population is expected to hit the 35 million mark in 2020.

1.7.1 ALIMOSHO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

The study area for this study is the Alimosho Local Government Area in Lagos State. Alimosho was established in 1945, under the then western region. It is bounded by Ifako Ijaiye, Agege and Ikeja Local Government Area in the East while Oshodi/Isolo, Amuwo Odofin and Ojo Local Government Areas of Lagos State bounds it to the West. Alimosho is located at the northernmost end of Lagos, and as a result, it connects Lagos State with Ogun State. Some areas of Alimosho are on the border of Lagos State, sharing close proximity to Ogun State's Ota, Lafenwa, and Agbado communities. Through Alimosho, the Lagos-Abeokuta Expressway connects Ogun State to Lagos State, passing. It is also surrounded by the neighbourhoods of Ikeja, Oshodi, and Agege.

1.7.1.1 Political Division

Alimosho local government area is located in the Ikeja division of Lagos state, and is often regarded as the State's largest local government area. The LGA consists of 6 Local Council Development Areas including: Agbado/Okeodo, Ayoba/Ipaja, Egbe/Idinmu, MosanOkunola, Ikotun/Igando, and Egbeda/Akowonjo. The first secretariat of Alimosho is a two-storey building located on Council street, in the present day Egbe/Idimu LCDA.

1.7.1.2 People and Population

Alimosho is also the most populous Local Government in Lagos State with a projected population of about 2,000,346 inhabitants in 2024 (Wikipedia). The 2006 Census had put the population of the Local Government at 1,319,571. However, the Lagos State Government argued that the population, as at 2006, within the LGA was over 2 million.

Majority of the population are from the Yoruba tribe, predominantly. The most commonly spoken languages in the area include Yoruba and English, while Christianity and Islam are mostly practiced in the area. The LGA is rich in culture, prominent amongst which are the Oro, Igunnu and Egungun annual festivals.

1.7.1.3 Geography of Alimosho

Alimosho local government area occupies a total land area of 183.5km² and an average temperature of 26.5 degrees centigrade with relative humidity of 80 percent. The two seasons witnessed in the area are the dry and the rainy seasons with total estimated precipitation of the area estimated at 2700 mm. The LGA originates from the Alashua river and it is located in coordinate of **6°36'38"N 3°17'45"E**.

1.7.1.4 Economy of Alimosho

The major economic activity in the area is Commerce with popular markets such as the Ikotun market, the Igando multi-purpose market and the Akesan market attracting thousands of buyers

and sellers on a daily basis. Alimosho LGA is also home to several privately and publicly owned institutions such as hotels and banks.

Fig 1a: Map of Nigeria showing Lagos State

Fig 1b: Map of Lagos State showing Alimosho Local Government Area

Fig 1c: Map of Alimosho Local Government Area

1.8 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1.8.1 Research Design

In carrying out this research, the methodology to be employed for this study is a survey design which focuses on residents of Alimosho Local Government, the study area. Both primary and secondary data will be used for the study. Data will be generated from residents through administration of structured questionnaires. Data obtained from the study area will be qualitatively analyzed.

1.8.2 Sources of Data

Both the primary and secondary data will be used for the study. The field survey (use of questionnaires) will be the source of primary data while secondary data will be sourced from online journals, articles, research works, published and unpublished works related to the study.

1.8.2.1 Primary Data

Primary data for this study will be obtained through the use of questionnaires and direct observations. The questionnaire will be designed in such a way that it contains series of well-structured questions according to the objectives of the study. These questions will be based on variables derived from the aim and objectives relevant to the study. The questionnaire will be divided into sections and administered to residents of the study area.

1.8.2.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data are information obtained through reading of materials related to the study, lecture notes, journals, as well as data collected from external bodies and portals.

The secondary data used will be sourced from websites of Government agencies, online journals, articles, research works, published and unpublished works related to the study. This data will be relied upon for literature review, etc.

1.8.3 Population of the Study

The populations considered for this study are the residents of Local Governments in Lagos Metropolis Area. The 2024 projected total population of Alimosho Local Government is 2,094,524.

1.9 SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Alimosho LGA 2006 Population (1,319,571)

Population estimation, using 2006 as a base year, was based on this formula:

$$P_1 = P_0 (1 + r)^n, \dots\dots\dots \text{Eq 3.1}$$

Where,

P_1 = **population as at 2024 (2024)**

P_0 = Based year population (2006)

1 = Constant

r = Rate of population growth per annum (2.6%)

n = Difference in the time interval (18 years)

2024 Population of Alimosho LGA = 2,094,524

➤ **NUMBER OF HOUSEHOLDS in Alimosho LGA at (5 members per household)=**
$$\frac{\text{Total Population}}{\text{Average household size}}$$

Number of household = 418,904 households

➤ **Sample size using Sample Size Calculator that was developed by Creative Research System (1982), USA**

Determine Sample Size

Confidence Level: 95% 99%

Confidence Interval:

Population:

Sample size needed:

Since the 36% of total households included migrants, the 36% of the sample size of the total household will be taken as sample size for migrants. This is based on International Organization for Migration (2019) that 36% of the Nigerian total households included migrants.

- The sample size for migrants is thus 97 households

The sample size of migrants will be equally distributed across the 11 wards in Alimosho LGA since there is no statistics on the variation in the population nor household size at the ward level. The sample size for each ward is (8.8) approximately 9 households per wards. The household heads of the migrated households will be interviewed using questionnaire. At the end, 99 questionnaires will be administered to household heads.

LIST OF WARDS (PAGE 45 of Polling unit file)= 11 WARDS

SN	Wards in Alimosho LGA	Sample Size
1	SHASHA/AKOWONJO	9
2	EGBEDA/ALIMOSHO	9
3	IDIMU/ISHERI OLOFIN	9

4	KOTUN/IJEGUN	9
5	EGBE/AGODO	9
6	IGANDO/EGAN	9
7	IPAJA NORTH	9
8	IPAJA SOUTH	9
9	AYOBO/IJON VILLAGE (CAMP DAVID)	9
10	PLEASURE/OKE-ODO	9
11	ABULE- EGBA/ABORU/MEIRAN/ALAGBADO	9
	TOTAL	99

1.9.1 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected from the respondents through questionnaires will be analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistical methods:

The descriptive statistical methods used include:

- i. The frequency tables,
- ii. Descriptive statistics and
- iii. Cross tabulations.

The inferential statistics used are:

- i. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA); and
- ii. Multiple Linear Regression

i. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), is a statistical test used to determine if there are significant differences between the means of three or more groups. It examines whether the variation in

the data is due to genuine differences between the groups or simply random chance. ANOVA is widely used in research to compare means across multiple groups and determine if the observed differences are statistically significant.

ANOVA was used to examine the association between the factors attracting migrants to Alimosho Local Government Areas. ANOVA was also used to examine the association between the factors pushing migrants out of their source regions.

The formula for ANOVA is given as:

$$F = MSB/MSE,$$

where F is the ANOVA statistic

MSB is the mean sum of squares between groups, and

MSE is the mean sum of squares within groups (or error).

ii. Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple Linear Regression analysis can help us to predict the values of dependent variables (Y) from the Independent variable (X). Regression analysis can also help to explain the magnitude of the change in the dependent variable given a unit change in the independent variable.

The Multiple Regression Analysis was used to examine the demographic characteristics of the respondents against the frequency of use of sustainable transportation.

The format of the regression model is:

$$Y = a + bX1 + bX2 + bX3 + bX4 + bX5 + bX6 + bX7$$

Where:

Y is the dependent variable – the level of challenge faced

X1 to X4 are the independent variables as defined below,

e is the error term

The dependent variable is the level of challenge faced

The independent variables used are: Gender, Marital Status, Education, Age, Occupation, Type of settlement migrated from, The nature of migration.

1.10 SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

This detailed study will explore how migration trends affects the population composition of Lagos, Nigeria, with a primary focus on the Lagos metropolitan area. The study will analyse how both internal and international migration affect the demographic composition of the city, its cultural environment and economic sectors. The study aims to examine the impact of both internal and international migration on Lagos' demographic structure. The research will also investigate the impact of migration on the population size and composition of the city of Lagos. These will be further supported by an in-depth examination of the major determinants of migration from other regions of Nigeria and abroad to Lagos. The study aims to shed light into on the major drivers of migration patterns and their potential effects and impacts. Additionally, the research will assess the driving factors affecting migration in the study area. This will include investigating how migration-induced population growth affects Lagos's infrastructure and public services, with emphasis on the challenges and opportunities that arise from rapid urbanization.

Despite the aim of the study to investigate the effect of migration and their impact on population distribution in Lagos, there are numerous limitations that may be encountered during the course of the research. They include:

Data Availability: Given how rapidly the population of Lagos is growing, the study may be limited by the accessibility and reliability of recent migration and population statistics.

Time and Resource Constraints: Long-term analysis of the study may be limited due to the nature of the research. Financial limitation may also affect the amount of data collected for the research.

Sample Size: The sample size adopted for the study may not adequately represent the diverse population of Lagos city. Since resources are limited, the researcher is unable to sample a large part of the population, hereby limiting the results of this study.

Communication Barriers: Difficulty in communicating with and gathering data from residents who do not speak English or the local language may also affect the results of the research.

Informal Settlements: Informal settlements and as ghettos, which often accommodate a significant migrant population, may be difficult to access to collect accurate data.

CHAPTER TWO

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 PREAMBLE

This chapter serves as a foundational exploration into the influence of migration patterns on population dynamics in Lagos, Nigeria. The Chapter explains the conceptual and theoretical frameworks relevant to the study of migration and its impacts on the population, and discusses existing literature reviews conducted by researchers. By discussing these, the chapter provides a comprehensive understanding of how migration patterns affects the population trends of cities and communities.

2.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1.1 Concept of Migration: Definitions and Categories

Koser (2016) defined Migration as “an integral part of human history. Human beings have been moving from place to place for social, economic, or political reasons from their earliest days”. Migration is usually explained in terms of time and space. Kok (2023) defined Migration “as the movement of people, usually involving a change in usual residence across an administrative boundary such as a village, town, district, or country”. Migration can be in the form of immigration, which is described as the number of people entering a receiving area, or emigration, which refers to the move and flow of people out of a country over a given period of time. Moreover, there are two types of migration: Internal, when migrants move within their own country; and International migration, a situation in which migrants move outside of their country of birth for at least one year (Poulain and Perrin 2023). Skeldon (2017) argued that migration, especially international migration, is a complicated concept because “its measurement depends entirely upon how it is defined in time and across space”. However, the

International Organization for Migration (IOM) has provided a better definition of international migration or a “migrant” by avoiding time and territorial limitations. A migrant is any person who is moving or has moved across an international border or within a State away from his/her habitual place of residence, regardless of (1) the person’s legal status; (2) whether the movement is voluntary or involuntary; (3) the causes for the movement are; or (4) what the length of the stay is (IOM, 2019).

The term “migrant” comprises a wide range of people, including those who are forced into exile. This is connected to the idea that people migrate voluntarily or involuntarily for socio-economic and political reasons (Bauman, 2023). Some people migrate voluntarily—referred to as “Tourists” in Bauman’s (2023) terms. Nevertheless, many migrants are forced to leave their own country due to persecution, war and extreme economic hardships in their home countries (UNHCR, 2018). The UNHCR (2018) further stated that such migrants carry out dangerous border crossings, and experience extreme displacement and hardship in transit countries. Yet, the world is not so friendly to forced migrants or, in Bauman’s terms, the “Vagabonds” (Bauman, 2023). They may be victims of xenophobic violence (Misago, 2016) and subjected to stricter immigration control, including detention and deportation. Migrants are further classified according to different labels based on the cause and destination of their movement, and their legal status in their country of destination.

Accordingly, the term “migrant” includes displaced people i.e. “individuals who are forced to move against their own will” (Shamsuddoha et al. 2023). People are also classified as internally or externally displaced depending on whether they crossed their countries’ borders or not. Internally displaced people flee their homes, but they remain within their country of origin. They are not entitled to refugee status under the UN convention but might receive a supply of relief materials such as food, medicines, and other basic facilities (International Committee of the Red Cross, 2023). Refugees often cross international borders due to a lack of protection

from their government. The 1951 Geneva Convention highlights the distinctive features of refugees. A refugee, according to the Convention is “a person who is outside his or her country of nationality or habitual residence, has a well-founded fear of being persecuted because of his/her race, nationality, membership of a particular social group, religion, or political opinion; and is unable or unwilling to avail him or herself of the protection of that country, or return there for fear of persecution”(UNHCR, 2011 as cited in Samson, 2023). Thus, the broad concept of migration includes refugees, who are externally displaced people, and other individuals who move from one place to another for socio-economic and political reasons. However, not all migrants are refugees. As can be understood from the above definition, refugees face a threat of persecution and lack the protection of their own country. In contrast, non-refugee migrants usually leave their country for reasons like employment, family, educational purpose, and enjoy their governments’ protection even when they are abroad. Based on the Geneva Convention, many countries have set eligibility criteria for determining the refugee status of individuals.

2.1.2 Concept of Population Dynamics

The seven most populous countries of the world, according to a 2021 World Population Review report, are China, India, United States, Indonesia, Pakistan, Brazil and Nigeria with population estimates of 1.444 billion, 1.393 billion, 332 million, 276 million, 225 million, 213 million and 211 million people respectively. The population growth rate of the countries, however, varies as China has a population growth rate of 0.34% while India, United States, Indonesia, Pakistan and Brazil has population growth rate of 0.97%, 0.58%, 1.04%, 1.95% and 0.67% respectively. Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa, has a population growth rate of 2.55% (World Population Review, 2021).

Population growth is an increase in the number of people living in a given area and its relationships with economic growth varies across countries. Population growth is one of the key issues facing developing countries in the world (Adeosun and Popogbe, 2021). Malthus propounded one of the most prominent theories of population growth, which states that “population growth contributes negatively to per capita income and deteriorates the human development index”. Population dynamics of an economy have serious effect on the economic growth and the welfare of a nation. Studies on population growth have always been relevant till the present. The world population was about 7 billion people in 2012 (Martin et al., 2021; New York Times, 2012); but records show that world population has increased tremendously over the last 10 years, with estimates suggesting further increase in the future. Recent estimates, according to a United Nations report, says that the world population has now reached an all time high 7.9 billion as of January 2022 (Malthus Population Clock, 2022; World Population Review, 2021). Population study experts and Economic analysts have also stated that the world population will continue to grow at a rapid rate over the next few decades, stressing natural resources, and with other negative impacts on economic development if countries cannot better manage the growth (United Nations Report, 2021). Drummond et al., (2023) noted that “About 80% of the projected 4 billion increase in global population will be accounted for by Africa in 2100”. Majority of developing countries around are currently experiencing high population growth due to high fertility rates and declining death rates. In the past, many countries of the world have regarded population growth and explosion as disastrous and a hindrance to economic growth and inimical to the improvement in the overall life of a people. In fact, many policy reviews on population have identified the negative influence of population dynamics on economic development of some countries of the world. However, recent studies reveal that population explosion can be a blessing rather than a curse as great benefits can be obtained from population growth, if properly harnessed (Wesley & Peterson, 2017).

2.1.3 Impact of Migration on Urban and Rural Development

In Nigeria, urban centres or cities are developing and people are migrating from rural to urban areas. They migrate for different reasons from rural to urban; these may be among others unemployment, lack of infrastructural facilities, educational institution etc. Afolayan (2020) opines that rural areas can be easily recognized using several criteria, except population. Such standards comprise the extent of infrastructural development i.e. road network, schools, water supply, electricity, health centres, communication, etc. Other standards employed include occupation, dwellings, level of community planning etc. Ezeah (2005 in Nweke, 2020) argued that rural areas are areas within the geographical space outside the densely developed towns, cities and sub-urban villages and whose inhabitants are primarily engaged in agriculture as well as, the most basic form of secondary and tertiary activities. Rural area, which is the opposite of an urban area, is the countryside whose inhabitants are engaged majorly in primary production activities including agriculture, fishing, and animal rearing (Ele, 2020). Nweke (2020) elaborated that about 90 percent of rural laborers in the labour force are directly or indirectly engaged in agriculture.

Typically, urban centers tend to gain growing importance with the growing pace of nation's development, for it is in such centers that a nation's potential is largely exhibited. The reality is that all the countries of the developing world are only on the threshold of their industrial take-off, and the concession of patents due to the former pattern of affairs in the Western world that industrialization and urbanization go hand in hand, attest the straightforward fact that unbroken rapid urbanization can but become inevitable in developing countries. According to Sorenson and Madu (2020) rural-urban migration is a result of the quest for perceived or actual opportunities due to rural-urban wealth inequality. This inequality and/or urban bias in development, according to research findings over the years, is a result of the very high

concentration of wealth, assets, purchasing power, economic activity, and variety of services in the urban centers and the widespread neglect and decline of rural habitats or areas (Harris and Todaro, 2016). The truth is that hitherto, the cities have been growing both naturally and by stampede from rural Nigeria. The reason behind the phenomenon has been referred to as the push forces in the rural areas and the pull forces in the urban areas. The magnitude of the forces created by these factors in the majority of Nigeria communities has made "push and pull" become understatement that can be replaced by "propulsive" and "magnetic". Goodness gracious, the rural communities are besieged by propulsive forces which propel the youths more than anybody else post haste to the towns which have the magnetic factors which sweep the rural communities in their inexorable field. Mabogunje (1968 as cited in Nweke, 2020) stated that in the majority of parts of the world, particularly the so-called Third World countries, it is inevitable that urbanization will continue to increase in the foreseeable future. The reality that most Third World nations are at the threshold of their industrial take-off, and the patent deviation from past experience in the Western world that urbanization and industrialization are inseparable trends, readily lead to the position that steady rapid urbanization is so far, inevitable in the third world.

2.1.4 Global Migration and Population Shifts

Trends in the world population have traditionally been based on a "slow demography paradigm" (Billari 2022) where differential mortality and fertility cause gradual changes in population size and composition. In contrast, migration may cause sudden demographic change in numbers, composition, and distribution of individuals, particularly at the regional level. This was vividly demonstrated during the COVID-19 pandemic when international border closure by countries globally impacted global patterns of migration (González-Leonardo et al. 2023). Systematic measurement of population distribution impacts from international migration were

until recent years constrained by scarcity of global data (Willekens et al. 2016). The last decade has seen significant advances, with the estimates of migration stocks, as well as bilateral migration flows, being produced (Abel & Cohen 2019). New evidence has introduced new insights into global migration patterns and trends. Most striking among them has been the relative stability in the size or intensity of global migration flows (De Haas et al. 2020). Despite this, recent decades have witnessed dramatic changes in international migration flows. Migrants are increasingly being recruited from more and more sources and are coming to focus in a smaller number of destination countries (de Haas, Castles and Miller 2019), creating a more concentrated global migration network (Tranos, Gheasi and Nijkamp 2015). Although most migration flows continue to occur between neighboring countries (UN 2019), migrants today travel longer distances (Czaika and de Haas 2020). Flows also switched directions with new source and destination locations. One aspect of international migration that has not yet been explored systematically is its impact, that is, the degree to which migration is redistributing the global population. Aimied at examining internal migration, the measures the spatial impact of migration are a function of the interaction of the intensity (i.e., degree of movement) and effectiveness of migration (i.e., degree of asymmetry of flows). Economic reasons largely drive international migration but demographic, environmental, policy, and political reasons also propel international migration (Sander et al. 2013). The scale of migration reflects origin and destination circumstances, mediated by distance-cost, and ought to differ in the future as countries grow to be developed. In cases of origins, emigration has been shown to have an inverted-U relationship with development (Clemens 2014). Emigration scale will, at first, be small due to the fact that individuals lack the resources to move abroad. Emigration increases as countries become wealthier, increasing the capacity of individuals to move and growing aspirations (De Haas 2020). The more developed the countries are, the lower

emigration is, as there will be low economic yields from migration, though emigration is bound to be greater than in the poor nations (de Haas 2020).

2.1.5 Impact of Migration Patterns on Population Dynamics

For destination countries, immigration is expected to increase linearly with development, with countries becoming more attractive as migrant destinations (De Haas 2020). At the global level, the rate of migration is expected to increase during the initial stages of global development, before it declines. Intensity is, however, unlikely to return to previous levels, with widespread ongoing circulation driven by extreme trade flows and cumulative causation in migration (Massey et al. 2016). The efficiency of international migration, i.e., the degree to which flows are countered by counter-flows, is a long-standing characteristic of migration dating back to Ravenstein's seminal work (Ravenstein 2019). As with intensity, effectiveness is a function of conditions in both origins and destinations. International migration among less developed countries will be low but volatile in its effectiveness, a function both of the low levels of permanent economic migration involved (even if there are large temporary flows), but also of the susceptibility of systems to shocks such as conflict and disaster-induced displacement. Migration effectiveness is expected to increase as emigration to high-income countries grows but has yet to be offset by backflows to less developed countries, i.e., return migration. Effectiveness for countries at later stages of development could fall as spatial equilibrium is reached because of equalizing immigration and emigration rates. This is not unavoidable: for internal migration we see contingent patterns of migration at more advanced stages of development such as the beginning of counter urban flows, increasing effectiveness (Rees et al. 2017). For international migration, selective migration policies can increase effectiveness, at least in the short term, as new migrant sources are tapped. Combined, intensification and effectiveness will bring about spatial impact shifts in the global population distribution but it

is yet unclear how both of these dimensions will combine to generate spatial impact in this research note, we examine the consequences of migration through the application of measures developed within the internal migration analysis literature (Bell et al. 2022) to novel estimates of international bilateral flows developed by Abel and Cohen (2019).

2.1.6 Perspective and Patterns of Migration

The phenomenon of migration has been a part of human life since the start of history because humans have always been involved in mobility activities. Internal and international migration is a common feature of both developing and developed countries. Internal migration in this context refers to the movement of individuals within their native country (in-migration and out-migration) due to any social, economic and political factor. International migration refers to the movement of individuals outside their native country (emigration) to another country (immigration) (Nwajiuba, 2005). Internal migration essentially covers the movement of individuals within same geographic space which in this case may be from rural to urban such as from Lagos to Abuja. International migration entails crossing boundaries or international borders such as Cameroon to Nigeria known as South-South Migration, or Nigeria to the United States of America known also as South-North Migration. Migration is a natural part of human existence, with a long history. Its trend, however, has greatly evolved over time, from one of space searching, especially in the middle ages, to one of concentration in large cities (rural-urban migration) in the modern era. This is especially so in the previous millennium. Three-fifths of the global population will be living in urban areas by 2030 (Stephens, 2000). Specifically referencing Africa and Nigeria, certain scholars notably Gopalkrishna & Oloruntoba, (2012) have attempted to root the underlying origins of migration in Africa in forced migration as a result of the precapitalist formations' response to the invasion of European merchant capital. They thus maintain that the colonial state in most African countries

introduced taxation which required able-bodied men to migrate to the urban centers to work so that they would obtain money to pay taxes. This pattern of migration caused massive disruption of the local production process due to the reality that able-bodied men left the rural areas to go to the urban centers. Similarly, Mberu (2010) noted for instance that Nigeria's experience of labour migration dates back to four phases of slave trade between 1400 and 1900 when over 12 million slaves were exported from west, west-central and east African countries (Nigeria being one of them) to the European Colonies in the Americas in the 15th century. Nigeria lost approximately 2 million forced labour migrants during this period of slavery (Dunn, 2008). The arrival of the British in the mid-19th century provided the conditions for large scale intraregional labour migration. They brought with them into the country export-oriented political economic policies, which essentially changed the face of migration and intraregional labour migration particularly in Nigeria. New resource-rich areas in north (groundnuts and tin) and southern (cocoa, kola nuts, rubber and coal) regions of Nigeria were opened up to sustain the colonial policy. The need for labour to keep up the production of these resources generated rural-rural migration of people to work as either migrant tenant farmers, farm workers, miners or migrant traders. Migrant workers were also drawn from other West African countries such as Burkina Faso, Niger, Chad, Mali, Guinea, Cape Verde, and Togo (Udo, 1975). Colonial political economic policies, led to unevenness in the provision of socio-economic services and infrastructure, which favored areas in the center of the political economic interest of the Colonial masters. The rural areas were thus neglected and left virtually abandoned. Although the concept of forced migration is mostly used to describe refugees, asylees and internally-displaced persons' movement (Castles, 2003), the inclination most describes the diasporization of Nigerians by economic imperatives as a forced migration case. In the foregoing, Obom-Egbulem (2010) finds that there are more than five thousand (5000) Nigerian Medical Doctors in the United States of America and the United Kingdom. While in Nigeria with an estimated

population of over one hundred and sixty million individuals (now estimated at 200 million); we have thirty-nine thousand, two hundred and ten (39,210) medical doctors.

2.1.7 Nigeria's Migration Trends and Population Dynamics

According to the International Organization for Migration (IOM), Africa has lost its top-level professionals over the years. To this regard, the IOM statistics provide that since 1990 an estimated total of 20,000 (twenty thousand) professionals (medical doctors, university lecturers, engineers, and others) leave the shores of the continent annually such that by 2007 there were over 300,000 highly skilled Africans in the diaspora (Okeke 2008). The Nigeria content in this composite is legible from the remittances within this context, the World Bank suggests that Nigeria takes the lead in Africa (World Bank 2012). The Nigerian State, for its part, has registered its own peculiar experiences of the flow of foreign immigrants. Thus, the relatively stable and booming economy of Nigeria after independence and the early 1970's attracted huge volumes of intraregional labour migrants from within and also ECOWAS member countries labour migrants, such as, Togo, Guinea, Cote d'Ivoire, Burkina Faso, Niger and Mali. These migrant workers were attracted to the already established enclaves of mining and cash crop farming, regional administrative towns of Enugu, Kaduna, Ibadan, and principal commercial centers and sea ports of Lagos, Port Harcourt, Calabar and Warri among others, where there were diverse employment opportunities. Internal migration, as Afolayan et al. (2008) reports, also gained momentum during the third and final quarter of the 20th century. Hence, the post-independence years experienced heightened labor migration from most areas of the nation to the nation's main administrative and economic centers and to increasingly diverse locations than ever previously. Relatively huge scale of immigration into the nation was upset by flight and/or expulsion. Besides, human movement was never solely spurred by economic reasons; ethnic conflict and internal war had prompted minorities to displacement

from the place of destination to the area they were from. The 1967-1970 Biafran War recorded the most massive displacement and displacement of various ethnic groups from the north to the southern and south-western parts of the country.

2.1.8 Migration Policies in Nigeria

Nigeria lacked a national strategic framework on migration for decades to inform the debate on migration within and outside the country. The key Working Document guiding migration in Nigeria is the 2015 adopted National Migration Policy (NMP). The National Migration Policy (NMP) is guided by a series of principles, among which are but not limited to the following: International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families, and the Palermo Protocol, for guarding migrants' rights against exploitative labor, human trafficking and smuggling, discrimination, and other malpractices which might flow from migration.

Notably, of key concern to the Policy is the free movement of nationals, as guaranteed in the 1999 Constitution, which reads in section 15(3), Chapter II, that the State shall "provide adequate facilities for and encourage free mobility of people, goods and services throughout the Federation.". The policy also acknowledges the framework of the new Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) Treaty, specifically Article 59, as well as the Protocol on the Free Movement of Persons, Residence and Establishment (Protocol A/P.1/5/79 of 1979) and later Supplementary Protocols of 1985, 1986, 1989 and 1990. The ECOWAS Common Approach on Migration, 2008, also advises the formation of this policy, specifically in enhancing intraregional mobility, making immigration and emigration easier with adequate institutions at leaving and receiving points within the region; maximizing regular migration to nations outside the ECOWAS region, examining useful means of managing migration and regulating irregular migration, as well as protecting the rights of migrants, refugees and asylum

seekers at destination nations; and incorporating the gender dimension into migration policies (ECOWAS Commission). The framework for the formulation of this policy was also guided by the AU Strategic Framework on Migration and Development and the AU Common Position on Migration and Development, 2006, in a variety of areas, such as human resources, irregular migration, brain drain, remittances, trade etc.

Nigeria has also ratified a variety of pertinent conventions and treaties, including the Convention against Torture and Other Inhuman, Cruel, Degrading Treatment or Punishment in 1984 (dated 28 June 2001); the African (Banjul) Charter on Human and Peoples' Right in 1981 (22 June 1983); the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child in 1990 (23 July 2001); the UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime in 2000 (28 June, 2001); the 2000 Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air, supplementing the UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (27 September 2001); the UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (1 November 1989). The Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children, adopted in 2000 and adding to the UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, was signed on 28 June 2001. In addition to Nigeria has ratified the eight core conventions of the International Labour Organization (ILO), in particular Convention 97 regarding Migration for Employment. Similarly, Nigeria is an active member of ECOWAS. Freedom of movement is guaranteed in the ECOWAS Protocol of 29 May 1979 on the Free Movement of Persons, Right of Residence and Establishment. This protocol allows ECOWAS citizens: (a) visa-free entry into any ECOWAS state; (b) visa-free residence of up to 90 days in any ECOWAS member state; and (c) application, after 90 days, for a permanent residence permit that will allow them to invest, start enterprises and work. In 2000, an ECOWAS passport was established. To date, the first step – abolition of visa requirements if the stay does not last longer than 90 days – has been successful. The target of the second stage, the right of residence,

and of the third and last phase's right of establishment has not yet been achieved. Partly due to these advances, the last decade has also seen a greater speed in the formulation of national migration and sectoral policies among African countries, to provide an operational platform and coordinating mechanism for the administration of migration. Although these advances have been made, Nigeria has no national strategic framework on migration to drive the discourse on migration both within and beyond the country. This migration policy is therefore well-timed, inclusive and addresses the priority aspects of migrants' rights as well as their development contribution, in line with existing national legal and policy tools of the country. The Federal Government of Nigeria delegates the coordination of Nigeria's national policy on migration to the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI), with the support of all the MDAs involved in migration and development programmes in Nigeria, for the implementation of this Policy. The inter-ministerial steering committee or TWG will be actively involved in implementing this policy to meet specific thematic issues in migration (see attached Action Plan Attached). During the four-day national workshop on "Migration Policy Development and Management in Nigeria" for the officials of the MDAs that was held in Abuja between 12-15 November 2012, the participants discussed their recommendations for issues that bear on the status of the draft national policy on migration. The major recommendations that come out of this are as follows: the need for greater visibility and autonomy of NCFRMI, for instance through direct reporting to Vice President or Office of the President; staffing NCFRMI with a chief executive officer with migration subject matter expertise; institutionalizing NCFRMI and increasing the capacity of the officials. Other Legal and Policy Regimes in Nigeria Relating to Migration:

a. Immigration laws

The law that regulates immigration issues in Nigeria is the Immigration Act of 1963. The other subsidiary rules are the Immigration Regulations of 1963; the Immigration (Control of Aliens) Regulations of 1963, and the Passport (Miscellaneous Provisions) Act of 1990.

b. Protection of migrants

Nigeria has ratified and signed the International Convention for the Protection of Migrant Workers and Members of their Families, which came into effect in 2003. The adoption of domestic legislation in this regard is one of the proposals in the ECOWAS Common Approach on Migration and also during the AU meetings.

c. Laws against trafficking in human beings and migrant smuggling

The Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, especially Women and Children (the Palermo Protocol) has been enacted as Nigerian national law by the Trafficking in Persons (Prohibition) Law, Enforcement and Administration Act of 14 July 2003. Amending Acts, published on 7 December 2005, extended the role of the National Agency for the Prohibition of Traffic in Persons (NAPTIP) to cover internal trafficking and exploitative child domestic work, and sanctioned the confiscation of convicted traffickers' assets and proceeds of crime. A Victims Trust Fund has also been set up, where forfeited funds are pooled to cater for victims' rehabilitation and compensation.

d. Child labour law/child rights/child trafficking

The Child Rights Act of 2003 is a lengthy document of 278 sections, making special provision for the prohibition of the worst forms of child labour, child marriage, child exploitation for the purpose of begging, recruitment of children into the Armed Forces, and child trafficking. Section 274 states that the provisions of the Act prevail over any other law. However, the Child Rights Act has not yet been domesticated by all the states – the northern states reported to be

having issues domesticating it – hence making the provisions of the Act inapplicable in all Nigerian courts.

e. The Labour Act of 1974/ 2004

The Labour Act of 1974, currently Labour Act CAP L1, LFN, 2004, prohibits the employment of children below the age of 15 years in industry and commerce, and restricts work performed by children to family or agricultural work within the home. The Act prohibits forced labour and provides that children cannot be used in agricultural or domestic work for more than eight hours a day and that children under the age of 12 years cannot be required to lift carry loads that could endanger their physical development. The act forbids the employment of people within and outside Nigeria, and the transportation of people for employment within and outside Nigeria. It also makes arrangements for the welfare of every individual who is employed.

2.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.2.1 Lee’s Theory of Migration

Everett Spurgeon Lee, Professor of Sociology at the University of Georgia is known for his pioneering theory of migration, which is known as the Push and Pull Theory, or also as Lee’ Theory. Lee first presented his model at the Annual meeting of Mississippi Valley Historical Association, Kansas City, in 1965. In 1966, his seminal work, ‘A Theory of Migration’, was published in Demography journal. The theory, which draws on principles of sociology, attempts to formalize a ‘theory’ of migration which would provide a scheme of the factors that could explain the volume of migration between origin and destination. Lee’s theory is both simple and has withstood the test of times.

Everett Lee has conceptualized the factors associated with the decision to migrate and the process of migration into the following four categories: (1) Factors associated with the area of

origin; (2) Factors associated with the area of destination; (3) Intervening obstacles; and (4) Personal factors.

Lee elaborates all these four categories by pointing out that, in each area, there are numerous factors which act to drive away the people from the area, or to hold the people in the area or to attract the people to it. In this respect, there are significant differences between the factors associated with the area of origin and those associated with the area of destination. Migration may take place after both these are properly weighed. Usually, however, a person has a better and more realistic knowledge about the place of origin, while his knowledge about the place of destination is somewhat superficial and inexact.

Intervening obstacles also have to be overcome before migration finally takes place. These include distance and transportation. Technological advances, however, have lessened their importance in modern times. Finally, the personal factors are of the utmost importance because, instead of the actual factors associated with the place of origin and/or destination, the individual's perception of these factors is found to influence the actual act of migration.

Push factors exist at the point of origin and act to motivate out migration (a lack of economic opportunities, education, etc., which are mentioned earlier). On the other hand, pull factors are present at the destination, which attract migrants (work opportunities and availability of jobs, conducive educational facilities, religious or political freedom. Push and pull factors are paired, that is, migration can occur if the reason of emigrating (the push) has a solution in the pull by destination. In the context of labor migration, the push factors are often characterized by the lack of job opportunities in sending areas or countries; and the pull factors are the economic opportunities available in the receiving areas.

Migration flow between two places—origin and destination—also depends on the intervening obstacles. These are the distance between the two places, lack of transport facilities,

inaccessibility because of the topography (rugged mountains and physical barriers), and restrictive immigration laws. The flow may not be strong in the presence of such intervening obstacles. The number of migrants is directly proportional to the extent of opportunities (the pull factors) available at the destination and inversely proportional to the intervening obstacles. The potential migrant may also consider the intervening obstacles as intervening opportunities, that is, the presence of other places between an origin and destination point to which one could migrate. Therefore, the volume of migration from one place to another is associated not only with the distance between places and number of people in the two places but also with the number of opportunities or obstacles between each place.

The theory suggests that migration is a result of the interaction between these push and pull factors. Individuals and families weigh the disadvantages of their current location against the advantages of a new place before making the decision to move.

Relevance to the Study

The Push-Pull Theory of Migration is highly relevant to the study of migration patterns and population dynamics in Nigeria. It provides a useful framework for analyzing why people move within and outside the country. By applying this theory, the study can identify and categorize the various economic, social, and environmental factors influencing migration in Nigeria. Understanding these factors will help elucidate the reasons behind both internal migration (e.g., rural-to-urban movement) and international migration (e.g., migration from Nigeria to other countries), and how they impact demographic changes, economic development, and social structures within the country.

2.2.2 Ravenstein's 'Law of Migration

Ravenstein's Law of Migration was first presented before the Royal Statistical Society on March 17, 1885. Ravenstein's original paper was based upon the British Census of 1881. In 1889, Ravenstein explored the subject further with data from more than twenty countries. Samers (2010: 55-56) points out that Ravenstein's laws are, in actuality, empirical generalisations based on his calculations from the British and other censuses of his time. They referred more to internal than international migration. These laws (or generalizations) are presented in a condensed form:

1. Migrants move mainly over short distances; those travelling longer distances head for the great centres of industry and commerce.
2. Most migration is from agricultural to industrial areas.
3. Large towns grow more by migration than by natural increase.
4. Migration increases with the development of industry, commerce, and transport.
5. Each migration stream produces a counter-stream.
6. Females are more migratory than males, at least over shorter distances. Males are dominant in international migration.
7. The major causes of migration are economic.

The first law (item number 1) proposes a gravity model of migration, which runs parallel to Newton's second law of motion, that the volume of movement between two places is directly proportional to the product of their masses (i.e. populations) and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them (White and Woods 1980: 39). Laws 2 and 3 concern rural-urban migration and urbanisation which are, historically, the main forms of population change in most countries of the world, even today. The fourth Law, related to migration for development, anticipated Zelinsky's (1971) famous 'hypothesis of the mobility transition' by

nearly a century to which we will return. Law 5 established the basis for the study of two-way migration dynamics, net migration, and return migration. Return migration became the subject of detailed study in the 1970s and 1980s. It remains an under-researched component of migration. Law 6 was even more pioneering: it introduced the gender element, which was ignored for nearly a hundred years since. The seventh law states a fundamental truism of most forms of migration.

In fact, Ravenstein's laws of Migration led to studies of the various influencing factors in migration: industrialization, sex, race, distance, education, the labour force, etc. However, most studies, which focused on the characteristics of migrants, were conducted with little reference to the volume of migration, the reasons for migration or the assimilation of the migrant at the destination. Regardless of the forms of migration or its duration, or how easy or how difficult it is, all acts of migration involve an origin, a destination, and an intervening set of obstacles. Of these obstacles, Lee (1966) included distance of the move as one that is always present.

2.3 LITERATURE REVIEW

Onwuka (2016) investigated the impact of population growth on economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2003 using OLS regression model. The study relied on annual time series data for its analysis with variables like GDP growth rate, population, population growth rate, lagged per capita output, among others of interest, also incorporated into the model. The empirical result showed that negative relationship existed between the core variables (i.e. population growth and economic growth) during the period considered. However, Adewole carried out a study to demystify highly controversial population impacts on Nigerian economic growth based on an annual time series data between 1981 and 2007. OLS regression technique was chosen by the researcher for analysis, real gross domestic product (RGDP), population and per capita income (PCI) are used in the model. The writer noted among other things that a

strongly positive correlation existed between population growth and economic growth (both in terms of RGDP and PCI) in the period of analysis. Oramah (2006) studied the effects of population growth on Nigeria economy in a double time growth study. The author highlighted the need for population control in Nigeria by translating the potential risk that is likely to be experienced as a result of neglecting trend whereby population is growing in the world. The author was more interested in addressing how population growth impacts consumption of non-renewable resources and depletion, land degradation and waste disposal, weather modification, urbanization and even desertification. Among the variables that have been found to influence population size in Nigeria include religion, education, male-child preference, old-age social security, high infant mortality etc. Nwosu, et al (2014) in an empirical study tested the relationship between population growth and economic growth in Nigeria from 1960 to 2008 using annual time series data. OLS techniques were combined with granger causality test for the study. The underlying variables that were employed in the model were population growth and GDP. Besides other discoveries, population growth was discovered to have a positive impact on economic growth in the time frame of observation; the authors were also able to prove that there is a long-run sustainable relationship between economic growth and population growth. Kothare (2016) conducted a research that sought to identify the relationship between economic growth and population growth in India. All the provinces in India were covered by the study, and the period 1988 to 1998 was discussed. The researcher applied the blend of analytical and descriptive statistical procedures on the data gathered on variables of interest from India. Empirical observation of the study revealed that economic growth was impacted positively by the growth of the population considerably, during the period under consideration. The researcher summed up by proving the result is valid for both short-run and long-run case. Ukpolo (2016) empirically measure the economic relationship between economic growth and population growth in Africa using Johansen and Granger-causality techniques. The study is on

the foundation of yearly time series data collected on the variables of interest from the two selected nations (Nigeria and Coted'ivoire). The results of the estimation showed that the variables are co-integrated, i.e., long run relationship existed between variables in Nigeria but not in Cote D'ivoire. The results further showed there is a negative long run causal relationship between the two variables of interest in Nigeria (i.e population growth has a negative effect on economic growth) in the long-run. In Coted'ivoire, the results showed population growth has a positive effect on economic growth in the short-run only.

Ogunbode, Adekunle & Abdullahi (2023) examined the internal migration patterns within Nigeria and their impact on demographic changes. The study utilized longitudinal data from national surveys, incorporating statistical analysis and demographic modeling to track migration trends. The research established significant shifts in demographic structure, such as increases in urbanization and regional differences in demographic structure. The research advocated for policy interventions to counteract urbanization challenges and ensure balanced demographic growth. Ajayi, Osunde & Afolabi (2021) examined the impact of international migration on Nigeria's demographics, considering trends and implications. To achieve this, they employed a comprehensive methodology comprising demographic data analysis, migration data analysis, and historical data analysis. The findings of their research indicated a massive contribution of foreign migration to the population dynamics of Nigeria, including shifting age structure and gender composition. Moreover, the research put into perspective the possible effect of such demographic changes, highlighting that there is a need for policy reform to adapt to the challenges and opportunities presented by international migration in Nigeria. Policymakers were encouraged to consider such demographic changes and their implication in formulating strategy plans for sustainable development and managing migration in the country.

The population demographics in the UK are also being revolutionized in terms of ethnic diversity and immigration patterns. Simpson, Leckie, Abrams & Tuffin (2018) observes that the ethnic minority population in the UK has been consistently growing because of immigration and ethnic minority births. For example, as per statistics by the ONS (2021), in 2020, 14.9% of British citizens were non-White compared to 9.1% as was in 2001. With such change having been brought about, diversity in work, cultural stimulation, and certain issues regarding multiculturalism as well as social integration occur. Urbanization also constitutes a core component of reformed UK demographics. The migration of people from rural to urban locations has resulted in the population concentrating in metropolitan cities and major cities. Champion (2017) explains that this has resource, housing, transport, and sustainability implications. For instance, London as a capital city has experienced a significant growth in population, which has put pressure on housing and transport infrastructure availability. United Kingdom's changing demography of aging society, ethnic diversity, and urbanization are showing changing patterns with far-reaching implications on the various spheres of society. Policymakers, researchers, and institutions are faced with the challenge and opportunities with regard to the changing demography. Japan is experiencing significant changes in its demography with increasing population that is aging very quickly, as well as decreasing rate of births. These are patterns mirrored in more current data, such as the figure of the United Nations Population Division (2020), showing that in 2019 Japan contained a population of approximately 126.5 million, where 28.1% were 65 and above and a birth rate as low as 1.42 children per woman. Japan's aging population is a critical population trend. Japan also has one of the highest life expectancies in the world, with the World Bank (2020) citing an average life expectancy of about 84 years in 2019. The rising life expectancy, combined with a falling birth rate, has resulted in a rapidly expanding elderly population. This demographic shift has long-term consequences for the Japanese workforce, social security schemes, and health care

services, with a growing demand for elderly care and a shrinking working-age population. Japan's declining birth rates are one of the key drivers of its demographic shift. Statistics by the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications (2021) show that Japanese births in 2019 hit a record low of 872,683. This is because of a variety of factors, including changed social norms, economic pressures, and delayed weddings. The Japanese family system is thus transforming with shrinking family sizes and increased proportions of older citizens, with implications for inter-generation relations and care reciprocities.

Sub-Saharan Africa has experienced unprecedented demographic changes over the past decades. The most striking trend is population increase in the region. Sub-Saharan Africa's population, according to Smith, Franklin & Bilsborrow (2017), has been growing at an unprecedented rate. The population increased by approximately 2.6% annually between 2010 and 2015, and it is projected to increase even more dramatically. This increase in population comes as a consequence of high mortality rates and low fertility rates. Sub-Saharan Africa is further characterized by its population being relatively young. Taking Lloyd et al. (2016) view, high percentages of the majority of countries in Sub-Saharan Africa fall into the population age group that is less than 25 years old. An example is the fact that approximately 43% of Nigeria's population is aged below 15 years (UN, 2020). This youth bulge has consequences on education, work and social services. Urbanization is another demographically significant trend in Sub-Saharan Africa. Grant & Yelvington (2019) observed the accelerated rate of urbanization in the region. Cities such as Lagos city in Nigeria and Nairobi city in Kenya have experienced increased population growth due to rural-urban migration. This trend has led to issues with infrastructure, housing, and availability of primary services. Sub-Saharan Africa is renowned for abundant cultural and ethnic diversity. That diversity manifests in population composition of countries like Ethiopia, where over 80 various ethnic groups coexist (Brotton, 2016). Ethnicity plays a significant role in shaping politics, social life, and identity in the

region. Population composition of ethnic groups is crucial to understand to address problems in governance and conflict. Life expectancy and health outcomes have improved in the majority of Sub-Saharan African countries. For instance, Wang, (2018) noted that life expectancy has improved in the region as a result of better healthcare and decreased prevalence of diseases such as HIV/AIDS. However, there are still enormous disparities within and between countries in terms of access to healthcare and outcomes. Nigeria, located in West Africa, has experienced significant changes in its population over time. The changes are characterized by dominating trends in growth of population, age structure, urbanization, and ethnic makeup. Nigeria's population, as indicated by Ukwuani & Suchindran (2019), has been steadily growing and is ranked among the topmost populous countries in Africa and the world. The population of Nigeria stood at approximately 140 million in 2006, and by 2019, it had surpassed 200 million, indicating a substantial increase in just over a decade. This rapid population growth has had profound implications for the country's social, economic, and political landscape.

ILO (2004) reported that migration has taken up a large number of youth entering the developed countries' labour markets, as well as remitting to the countries of origin. As reported from literatures, developing countries engage more in International Migration than the developed countries (International Organization Migration, 2014). About one billion migrants are global today not in their country of origin (International Federal Red Cross and Red Crescent, 2012) because such migrants globally can form a 6th country state after the order of China, Indian, United States of America (USA), Indonesia and Brazil (Martin and Widgren, 2002:3) as people move from a particular place to another because of various reasons best known to them also being part of man's nature (Adeola and Fayomi, 2012:1). Migration and economic growth are linked in various ways. Migration has contributed to poverty reduction, national security, political stability and reduced unemployment in the majority of the sending nations like Nigeria (GCIM, 2005). Cross-border migration generates significant economic

gains to the migrants initially, and later for the sending and receiving countries (World Bank, 2006). India recorded highest in 2012 at \$69.35 billion, followed by China (\$60.25 billion), Philippines (\$24.45 billion), Mexico (\$23.22 billion) and Nigeria (\$20.57 billion) (UNCTAD 2013). Most of the remittances are spent at micro levels on investment in businesses and human capital, family maintenance, weddings, donation to charitable organizations, tithes in churches and festive occasions. On the other hand, migrant remittances have also increased considerably over the last several years from \$1 billion in 2003 to \$20.6 billion in 2012 (OECD, 2012). Migrant remittances have also surpassed both FDI inflows and net Official Development Assistance (ODA) to Nigeria (Darkwah & Nahanga, 2014).

CHAPTER THREE

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

3.0 PREAMBLE

This chapter presents the results of the analysis on the questionnaires administered by the researcher in Alimosho Local Government Areas on the “Spatial Assessment of Migration and its Driving force”. A total number of ninety-nine (99) questionnaires were distributed to the respondents in eleven (11) wards of the local government. The data was analyzed using SPSS and frequency tables were used to explain the results. The hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Multiple regression analysis and interpretations were further made.

3.1 SOCIOECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

The table 3.1 presents a breakdown of the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents in Alimosho Local Government Areas, highlighting gender, marital status, educational qualification, age, occupation, and nationality.

The gender distribution in the sample consists of 43.4% male and 56.6% female respondents. This indicates a slight skew towards a higher number of female participants, with women making up the majority of the sample.

When examining marital status, the largest proportion of respondents (46.5%) are married. The second largest group is single individuals, making up 32.3% of the sample. There are also smaller groups of individuals who are separated (11.1%), divorced (7.1%), and widowed

(3.0%). This distribution shows that the majority of respondents are in stable marital relationships, while a smaller percentage are either separated, divorced, or widowed.

In terms of educational qualifications, a significant proportion of the respondents have either secondary education (42.4%) or tertiary education (43.4%). This suggests that most participants have received at least some level of formal education beyond the basic level. A smaller percentage of respondents have no formal education (11.1%), while only 3.0% have completed primary school education. These figures indicate that education is highly valued, with a clear majority of the sample being well-educated.

The age distribution shows that the majority of respondents (40.4%) are between the ages of 36 and 45. The next largest group is individuals aged 25 to 35, comprising 28.3% of the sample. The proportion of respondents under the age of 25 is 11.1%, and fewer respondents fall into the age brackets of 46-55 (15.2%) and 56-65 (5.1%). This data suggests that the sample is predominantly made up of individuals in the prime working age group, with fewer participants from the younger or older age categories.

The occupation distribution reveals that self-employed individuals make up the largest group, at 50.5%. Civil servants represent 23.2% of the sample, while smaller groups of respondents are employed in the private sector (7.1%), farming (6.1%), as students (6.1%), or retired (4.0%). A small percentage (1.0%) are unemployed. This distribution highlights a high level of entrepreneurial activity among the respondents, with many engaging in self-employment. The presence of individuals in civil service, farming, and private organizations further reflects the diversity of occupations among the population.

All the respondents are Nigerian, as indicated by the 100% representation in the Nigerian category. There were no non-Nigerian respondents in the sample.

Table 3.1 Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

Socioeconomic Characteristics		Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	43	43.4
	Female	56	56.6
Marital Status	Single	32	32.3
	Married	46	46.5
	Divorced	7	7.1
	Widowed	3	3.0
	Separated	11	11.1
Educational Qualification	No formal education	11	11.1
	Primary School	3	3.0
	Secondary School	42	42.4
	Tertiary	43	43.4
Age	Less than 25	11	11.1
	25 - 35	28	28.3
	36 - 45	40	40.4
	46 - 55	15	15.2
	56 - 65	5	5.1
Occupation	Student	6	6.1
	Civil Servant	23	23.2
	Self-employed	50	50.5
	Farming	6	6.1
	Unemployed	1	1.0

	Retired	4	4.0
	Private Organization	7	7.1
	Others	2	2.0
Nationality	Nigerian	99	100.0
	Non-Nigerian	0	0
Total		99	100.0

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Table 3.2 shows the respondents' states of origin distribution with notable variation in the number of respondents from each state. The state with the highest number of respondents is Ogun, with 18 participants, making up 18.2% of the total sample. This suggests that Ogun has a significant representation among the individuals surveyed. Other states with relatively high representation include Oyo (13.1%) and Ondo (9.1%), with 13 and 9 respondents, respectively. These states contribute notably to the sample, showing a strong regional presence from the southwestern part of Nigeria. Several other states, such as Kogi and Kwara, both represent 6.1% of the sample, with 7 and 6 respondents, respectively. Imo also has a similar level of representation, contributing 6.1% of respondents (6 participants). These states also play a key role in the distribution, particularly from the southeastern and central regions. Other states with moderate representation include Osun (10.1%), Akwa Ibom (3.0%), Kano (3.0%), and Ekiti (4.0%), each contributing a varying but significant proportion to the sample.

Interestingly, there are several states with only one or two respondents, such as Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, and Rivers, which together account for a smaller portion of the sample (between 1.0% and 2.0% each). These states, while present, have less influence on the overall distribution.

Table 3.2 State of Origin of Respondents

State of Origin	Frequency	Percent (%)
Abia	2	2.0
Akwa Ibom	3	3.0
Anambra	2	2.0
Bayelsa	1	1.0
Cross River	1	1.0
Delta	1	1.0
Edo	2	2.0
Ekiti	4	4.0
Enugu	2	2.0
Imo	6	6.1
Jigawa	2	2.0
Kaduna	2	2.0
Kano	3	3.0
Kebbi	2	2.0
Kogi	7	7.1
Kwara	6	6.1
Ogun	18	18.2
Ondo	9	9.1
Osun	10	10.1
Oyo	13	13.1

Rivers	1	1.0
Sokoto	2	2.0

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Table 3.3 further provides a summary of three key descriptive statistics: the number of migrated household members, average income per day, and the year of migration.

The number of migrated household members ranges from 0 to 9, indicating that some households have no migrated members, while others have up to 9 members who have migrated. The minimum value of 0 suggests that there are households in the sample where no one has migrated, while the maximum of 9 highlights that certain households have a substantial number of migrants.

The income data ranges from 0 to 200,000, with a total of 95. The minimum income of 0 suggests that some individuals do not earn any income, which could be due to various reasons such as unemployment, low-paying jobs, or other economic factors. The maximum income of 200,000 indicates that a small number of individuals earn a high daily income, which is significantly above the average for the broader population.

The year of migration ranges from 1 to 35, with respondents reporting that their migration occurred between 1 and 35 years ago. This suggests that migration experiences span several decades, with some individuals migrating recently (within the past year) and others having migrated many years ago. This range indicates that migration is a long-standing phenomenon for some, while others have experienced more recent migration events.

Table 3.3 Descriptives of Respondents

Descriptives	N	Minimum	Maximum
Number of migrated household members	99	0	9

Average Income per Day	95	0	200000
Year of Migration	99	1	35

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2025

3.2 SPATIAL PATTERN AND CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRATION

The table 3.4 shows the type of area the respondents migrated from between rural and urban areas. A majority of the respondents (80.8%) migrated from urban areas, while only 19.2% migrated from rural areas. This suggests that urban-to-urban migration is far more common within the sample than rural-to-urban or rural-to-rural migration. The higher migration rate from urban areas reflects possibly more opportunities for migration in cities, including education, employment, and social networks that facilitate such movements.

For the type of residency, the table shows that the majority of respondents (77.8%) have permanent residency, while 22.2% have temporary residency. The larger proportion of permanent residency indicates that most migrants have settled in their new locations, likely as part of a long-term or permanent relocation., while the smaller percentage of temporary residents suggests that some individuals may have moved for short-term opportunities or remain in a migratory state, possibly due to factors like temporary work assignments, studies, or seasonal employment.

The nature of migration further reflects the choices and circumstances surrounding the movement of individuals. A significant majority (88.9%) of the respondents migrated voluntarily, indicating that most migration was based on personal choice or aspiration—such as pursuing better job prospects, education, or improved living conditions. In contrast, 11.1% of respondents migrated due to forced circumstances, which could include displacement due to conflict, economic hardship, or environmental factors like natural disasters. The predominance

of voluntary migration suggests a higher level of agency and decision-making among the respondents in their migration patterns.

Table 3.4 Spatial Pattern and Characteristics of Migration

Spatial Pattern & Characteristics of Migration		Frequency	Percent (%)
Type of area migrated from	Rural	19	19.2
	Urban	80	80.8
Type of residency	Permanent	77	77.8
	Temporary	22	22.2
Nature of Migration	Forced	11	11.1
	Voluntary	88	88.9
Total		99	100.0

Source: Author’s Field Work, 2025

Figure 3.1: Pie chart showing the nature of migration

Figure 3.2: Map of Alimosho Local Government Area showing the nature of Migration to the Local Government

Source: Generated with ArcGIS, 2025

Table 3.5 reveals a breakdown of the states from which respondents migrated, highlighting the distribution of migration across various regions of Nigeria. Ogun state has the highest representation, with 35 respondents, making up 35.4% of the total sample. This indicates that Ogun is a primary origin state for migration within the surveyed population, with a significant proportion of individuals having migrated from there. Other states with relatively high migration frequencies include Oyo (12.1%) and Imo (7.1%). Oyo, in particular, stands out with 12 respondents, reflecting a considerable migration flow from that state. Imo follows with 7 respondents, accounting for 7.1% of the sample. These states contribute significantly to the overall migration distribution. Several other states such as Kwara (5.1%), Ondo (5.1%), and Kogi (4.0%) also have notable migration frequencies. While the representation from these states is smaller than Ogun, Oyo, and Imo, they still contribute a decent portion of the total respondents. Smaller groups of migrants come from states like Ekiti, Osun, and Akwa Ibom, each contributing 4.0% or 3.0% of the total sample. These states represent a moderate portion of the migrant population. On the other hand, some states such as Abia, Anambra, and Edo each contribute 2.0% of the sample, with only a few respondents migrating from these regions. States like Abuja, Cross River, Delta, Kebbi, and Sokoto each have only one respondent, representing 1.0% of the total migration sample.

Table 3.5 State of Migration of Respondents

State of Migration of Respondents	Frequency	Percent (%)
Abia	2	2.0
Abuja	1	1.0
Akwa Ibom	3	3.0

Anambra	2	2.0
Cross River	1	1.0
Delta	1	1.0
Edo	2	2.0
Ekiti	4	4.0
Enugu	2	2.0
Imo	7	7.1
Kaduna	2	2.0
Kano	3	3.0
Kebbi	2	2.0
Kogi	4	4.0
Kwara	5	5.1
Ogun	35	35.4
Ondo	5	5.1
Osun	4	4.0
Oyo	12	12.1
Sokoto	2	2.0

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Figure 3.3: Map of Nigeria showing Respondents State of Migration to the Local Government

Source: Generated with ArcGIS, 2025

3.3 DRIVERS OF MIGRATION IN ALIMOSHO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

Findings from table 3.6 reveals the attracting factors that draw the respondents to Alimosho Local Government Area (LGA). It shows that Job opportunities are a key attracting factor for respondents, with 31 participants rating it as "Very high" and 23 rating it as "High." This shows that employment prospects play a significant role in drawing people to Alimosho, with a majority of respondents perceiving it as a major benefit of living in the area. Only 1 person rated it as "Very low," indicating that job availability is a widely recognized and valued factor for those moving to the LGA.

Better housing is another important factor, with 29 respondents rating it as "Very high" and 18 rating it as "High." The moderate to high ratings suggest that housing quality and availability are key considerations for individuals looking to settle in Alimosho. However, there is a more mixed response compared to job opportunities, with 2 individuals rating it as "Very low" and 8 as "Low." This indicates that while many individuals view housing in the area as an attraction, it may not be the most universally compelling factor.

Social networks, which include connections with friends, colleagues, or community groups, appear to have a moderate influence on migration to Alimosho. A significant portion (51 respondents) rated it as "Moderate," with another 30 respondents rating it as "High." The number of people rating it as "Very low" (0) indicates that social networks are at least somewhat relevant to everyone surveyed. However, the lower "Very high" ratings (5) suggest that this factor does not carry the same weight for many respondents as job opportunities or housing.

The urban lifestyle have a mixed response with 53 respondents rated it as "Moderate," only 18 rated it as "High," and 13 as "Very high." This suggests that for some individuals, the urban environment of Alimosho is a significant draw, offering advantages like convenience, infrastructure, and entertainment. However, the low number of "Very high" responses (13) indicates that the urban lifestyle may not be the primary motivating factor for most respondents.

The presence of family and friends is an attractive factor for 25 respondents, who rated it as "Very high," and 19 rated it as "High." The presence of social support networks is an important pull factor for those migrating to the area, indicating that personal relationships and community ties are crucial considerations. However, there is also a notable proportion of respondents (30) who rated it as "Low," and 2 who rated it as "Very low," indicating that family and friends may not be the dominant factor for everyone.

Table 3.6 Factors that attracts respondents to Alimosho Local Government Area

Attracting Factors to Alimosho Local Government Area	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High
Job opportunities	1	10	34	23	31
Better housing	2	8	42	18	29
Social Networks	0	13	51	30	5
Urban Lifestyle	1	14	53	18	13
Family/friends	2	30	23	19	25

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Table 3.7 outlines the push-out factors from respondents' source regions, which represent the conditions or challenges that compel individuals to migrate from their areas of origin.

Insecurity stands out as a significant factor, though with a mixed response. A majority (52 respondents) rated it as "Low," while 24 respondents rated it as "Moderate." Only 10 respondents rated it as "High," and a very small number (2 respondents) rated it as "Very high." This suggests that insecurity is a notable issue for some, but it is not the dominant push-out factor for most. The relatively high number of "Low" ratings suggests that insecurity may be a concern for some areas but not universally seen as a highly severe factor driving migration.

War is a highly significant push factor for a large portion of respondents, with 60 individuals rating it as "Very low," reflecting that war is not an immediate concern for most. However, 30 respondents rated it as "Low," and a smaller number (6) rated it as "Moderate." Only 2 respondents rated it as "High," and just 1 person rated it as "Very high." This suggests that war, while impactful in certain regions, is not a widespread driver of migration in this sample. The responses indicate that most individuals do not perceive war as a primary reason for their migration, although it remains a significant concern for some.

Unemployment emerges as a critical push factor, with 29 respondents rating it as "Very high" and 21 as "High." A significant portion (40 respondents) rated it as "Moderate." The high ratings in the "High" and "Very high" categories highlight that unemployment is a strong motivator for migration, as people seek better job opportunities elsewhere. A smaller percentage rated it as "Very low" or "Low" (4 and 5 respondents, respectively), indicating that while unemployment is a major push factor, it does not affect everyone equally.

Marriage is another push factor that shows some variation in its significance. A substantial number of respondents (26) rated it as "Low," while 25 rated it as "Moderate." Interestingly, 23 respondents rated it as "Very high," suggesting that marriage plays a significant role for some individuals in deciding to migrate. Marriage may influence people to move to be with a spouse or start a family elsewhere. This factor appears to be a notable, but not dominant, reason for migration compared to unemployment or insecurity.

Transfers, likely referring to job or educational relocations, show a significant distribution across responses. A total of 41 respondents rated it as "Low," while 23 rated it as "Moderate," and 13 rated it as "High." Only 9 respondents rated it as "Very high." This indicates that while transfers are a push factor for some, it is not as prevalent or universally impactful as factors like unemployment or insecurity. Many individuals likely migrate due to work-related transfers, though it is not the leading reason for most respondents.

Family issues, which may include factors like caregiving, domestic responsibilities, or family conflicts, show a relatively moderate impact on migration decisions. A total of 33 respondents rated it as "Low," and 21 rated it as "Moderate." However, 15 individuals rated it as "Very high," and 12 rated it as "High." Family-related issues appear to be a significant but not overwhelmingly dominant reason for migration in this sample. The presence of higher ratings

in the "Very high" and "High" categories suggests that personal family concerns are important for some respondents.

Poor living conditions, including inadequate infrastructure, housing, or basic services, are a significant push factor for many respondents, with 27 rating it as "High" and 20 as "Very high." This indicates that substandard living conditions are a prominent driver for migration, particularly for individuals seeking better living standards. On the other hand, 24 respondents rated it as "Low," and 24 rated it as "Moderate," showing that not everyone considers poor living conditions as a major issue, though it affects a large portion of the sample.

Table 3.7 Factors that push out respondents from their source region

Push-Out Factors from source of region	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High
Insecurity	11	52	24	10	2
War	60	30	6	2	1
Unemployment	4	5	40	21	29
Marriage	6	26	25	19	23
Transfer	13	41	23	13	9
Family issues	18	33	21	12	15
Poor living conditions	2	24	24	27	20

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

3.4 CHALLENGES FACED BY MIGRANTS IN ALIMOSHO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

The table 3.8 provides the challenges faced by migrants in Alimosho Local Government Area (LGA). It reveals that a significant number of respondents (64.6%) indicated that they did not face a lack of employment opportunities, while 35.4% reported that employment opportunities were a challenge. This suggests that while many migrants may find employment in Alimosho LGA, a larger portion still struggles to secure stable or adequate jobs.

As regards housing conditions, a majority of respondents (78.8%) reported not facing poor housing, but 21.2% of respondents indicated that poor housing was indeed a challenge. However, the 21.2% who are impacted points to a segment of the population dealing with substandard housing, which could include overcrowding or inadequate facilities.

In terms of healthcare access, 65.7% of respondents stated they did not face inadequate healthcare access, while 34.3% reported difficulties in accessing adequate healthcare services. This shows that a significant proportion of migrants may experience challenges related to healthcare, possibly due to factors like affordability, availability of facilities, or quality of care.

Social issues like discrimination or social exclusion were reported by 29.3% of respondents, while 70.7% did **not** experience these challenges. The relatively smaller percentage of individuals facing discrimination may suggest that, while not widespread, social exclusion still affects some migrants in Alimosho.

Security concerns are minimal, with 92.9% of respondents indicating that they do not face security issues, and only 7.1% reporting security concerns as a challenge. This indicates that security in Alimosho is generally not a major issue for migrants, and most feel safe in their new environment. The small proportion of respondents affected by security issues might reflect localized concerns, but it does not appear to be a widespread challenge.

Access to education is a significant concern, with 58.6% of respondents stating they faced limited access to education, while 41.4% did not report such a challenge. This highlights that

a large portion of migrant families or individuals in Alimosho face barriers to education, potentially due to factors such as cost, availability of schools, or other socioeconomic constraints. Education is a crucial factor in improving opportunities for future generations, and the limitation in access can affect the long-term prospects of migrant communities.

From the rating of levels of challenges identified by the respondents, it is evident that a significant number of respondents perceive their challenges as moderate to very high, with 50.5% considering their challenges to be of moderate severity. The combined 38.4% (19.2% for high and 19.2% for very high) indicates that a notable portion of the migrant population faces significant challenges that could impact their livelihoods and integration into the local community. The relatively small percentage of respondents who rated their challenges as "very low" or "low" suggests that the majority of migrants face some level of difficulty in their new environment.

Table 3.8 Challenges Faced by Migrants in Alimosho Local Government Area

Challenges Faced by Migrants Alimosho LGA		Frequency	Percent (%)
Lack of Employment opportunities	No	64	64.6
	Yes	35	35.4
Poor housing conditions	No	78	78.8
	Yes	21	21.2
Inadequate access to healthcare	No	65	65.7
	Yes	34	34.3
Discrimination or social exclusion	No	70	70.7
	Yes	29	29.3
Security concerns	No	92	92.9
	Yes	7	7.1
Limited access to education	No	41	41.4

	Yes	58	58.6
Rating the level of challenge identified	Very low	1	1.0
	Low	10	10.1
	Moderate	50	50.5
	High	19	19.2
	Very high	19	19.2
Total		99	100.0

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Figure 3.4 Pie chart showing the rating of level of challenges identified

Figure 3.5: Map of Alimosho Local Government Area showing the challenges faced by Migrants to the Local Government

Source: Generated with ArcGIS, 2025

Figure 3.6: Map of Alimosho Local Government Area showing the rating of challenges faced by Migrants to the Local Government

Source: Generated with ArcGIS, 2025

3.5 MEANS OF IMPROVING LIVELIHOOD OF MIGRANTS IN ALIMOSHO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

Table 3.9 summarizes the means through which migrants' livelihoods can be improved in Alimosho Local Government Area (LGA), as well as suggestions for how policymakers can better manage migration-driven population growth. It reveals 10.1% of respondents identified employment opportunities as a key factor for improving migrants' livelihoods. This suggests that while a portion of the migrant population sees job availability as an important aspect of enhancing their quality of life, it may not be the most widely prioritized measure. The largest group of respondents (23.2%) pointed to affordable housing as the most important factor for improving livelihoods. This indicates that a significant number of migrants view the availability of decent and affordable housing as a critical need. Housing is a fundamental aspect of quality of life, and its affordability can significantly impact the well-being of migrant populations. Also, 17.2% of respondents emphasized the importance of access to education and skill development programs. This highlights the need for opportunities that allow migrants to improve their knowledge, skills, and qualifications, which could open doors to better employment opportunities and social mobility.

Only 1% of respondents selected improved healthcare facilities as a means to improve livelihoods. Although this is the least mentioned factor, it still reflects the importance of access to affordable and quality healthcare services for the migrant population. Moreover, 42.4% of respondents identified financial assistance or loans as an essential means to improve livelihoods. This is the most frequently mentioned support, indicating that migrants may need financial help to start businesses, support their families, or invest in opportunities that can improve their socio-economic standing. Access to financial resources can be a significant enabler, particularly for self-employed migrants or those trying to invest in education or

housing. Additionally, 6.1% of respondents mentioned other forms of support to improve livelihoods. While this category includes responses that are not clearly defined, it demonstrates that there are additional, diverse needs that may not have been captured by the predefined options.

On the ways policymakers can better manage migration-driven population growth, 12.1% of respondents suggested that improving urban planning would help manage migration-driven population growth. 13.1% of respondents believed that developing affordable housing is a crucial policy measure. 17.2% of respondents saw enhancing public transportation as a critical policy priority. The largest portion of respondents (36.4%) emphasized the need to create more job opportunities. This reflects the widespread concern that employment is a key factor in improving migrants' livelihoods and integrating them into the local economy. Also, 8.1% of respondents suggested that investing in infrastructure is an essential policy action. Lastly, 13.1% of respondents proposed other actions to manage migration-driven population growth.

Table 3.9 Means of Improving Livelihood of Migrants in Alimosho Local Government Area

Means of Improving Livelihood of Migrants		Frequency	Percent (%)
Type of support to improve livelihood	Employment opportunities	10	10.1
	Affordable housing	23	23.2
	Access to education and skill development programs	17	17.2
	Improved healthcare facilities	1	1.0
	Financial assistance or loans	42	42.4
	Others	6	6.1

Ways policymakers can better manage migration-driven population growth	Improve urban planning	12	12.1
	Develop affordable housing	13	13.1
	Enhance public transportation	17	17.2
	Create more job opportunities	36	36.4
	Invest in infrastructure	8	8.1
	Others	13	13.1
Total		99	100.0

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Figure 3.7: Pie chart showing ways policymakers can better manage migration

3.6 TEST OF HYPOTHESES

The first hypothesis was tested using the ANOVA to examine the association between the factors attracting migrants to Alimosho Local Government Areas. The data was analyzed based on the results from table 3.6. The hypothesis is stated thus:

H01: There is no significant association between the factors attracting migrants to Alimosho Local Government Areas

The table 3.10. shows the results of an ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test, which helps determine if there are significant differences between the factors that influence migration to Alimosho. The sum of squares indicates the total variation in the data. The "Between Groups" sum of squares (4027.600) represents the variation due to differences between the factors attracting migrants, while the "Within Groups" sum of squares (1528.400) represents the variation within each group or factor. The degrees of freedom (df) measure the number of independent pieces of information and for between-group variation is 4 (corresponding to 5 groups minus 1), and for the within-group variation, it is 20. The mean square for between groups is 1006.900, and for within groups, it is 76.420. The F-value is 13.176 and it tests the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the groups. The p-value is 0.000, which is much lower than the common significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the results are statistically significant, meaning that there is a significant association between the factors attracting migrants to Alimosho. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H01) and conclude that there is a significant relationship between the factors influencing migration to Alimosho.

Table 3.10 ANOVA of association between the factors attracting migrants to Alimosho Local Areas

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4027.600	4	1006.900	13.176	.000
Within Groups	1528.400	20	76.420		
Total	5556.000	24			

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

Hypothesis two was also tested using the ANOVA to examine the association between the factors pushing migrants out of their source regions. The data was as well analyzed based on the results from table 3.7. and the hypothesis states that:

H02: There is no significant association between the factors pushing migrants out of their source regions.

According to table 3.11, the hypothesis tested whether there is no significant association between the factors pushing migrants out of their source region. The ANOVA results show that the F-value is 2.640, and the p-value is 0.053, which is slightly above the common significance level of 0.05.

Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that there is no statistically significant association between the factors pushing migrants out of their source region.

Table 3.11 ANOVA of association between the factors pushing out migrants from their source region

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2640.971	4	660.243	2.640	.053
Within Groups	7504.000	30	250.133		
Total	10144.971	34			

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

To test Hypothesis three, the Linear Multiple Regression was employed to examine the predictors of the levels of challenges faced by migrants. The dependent variable is the level of challenge faced and the independent variables used are: Gender, Marital Status, Education,

Age, Occupation, Type of settlement migrated from and the nature of migration. The hypothesis tested is thus stated:

H03: There is no significant relationship between the level of challenge faced by the migrants and their socio-economic characteristics

Table 3.12 reveals the model summary showing a moderate relationship between the variables, with an R value of 0.367. However, the R Square value of 0.135 indicates that only 13.5% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the model. The Adjusted R Square (0.068) is lower, suggesting limited explanatory power. The standard error of 0.918 indicates considerable prediction error.

Table 3.12 Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.367	0.135	0.068	0.918

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

The ANOVA table from table 3.13 shows that the regression sum of squares is 11.922, with 7 degrees of freedom for the regression and 91 for residuals. The F-value is 2.023, and the p-value is 0.061, which is above the 0.05 significance level. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the regression model is not statistically significant and does not explain the variation in the dependent variable.

Table 3.13 ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	11.922	7	1.703	2.023	.061(a)
Residual	76.623	91	.842		

Total	88.545	98			
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Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

The coefficients table presents the results of a regression analysis, showing the impact of various predictors (socioeconomic characteristics) on the dependent variable (level of challenges faced by migrants). The constant, which represents the predicted value of the dependent variable when all other variables are zero, is 5.050 and is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000.

Among the predictors, gender has a significant negative effect on the dependent variable, with a coefficient of -0.439 and a p-value of 0.046. This suggests that gender is a significant factor, negatively influencing the outcome. Similarly, marital status has a significant positive effect with a coefficient of 0.214 and a p-value of 0.017, indicating that being married positively impacts the dependent variable. On the other hand, education has a coefficient of -0.048 and a p-value of 0.644, showing that it does not significantly affect the dependent variable. Similarly, age, with a coefficient of -0.166 and a p-value of 0.162, also does not have a statistically significant impact. The variable occupation shows a coefficient of 0.040 and a p-value of 0.526, further indicating that it is not a significant predictor of the dependent variable. The type of settlement migrated from and the nature of migration both have coefficients of -0.092 and -0.409, respectively, but their p-values are 0.724 and 0.197, suggesting that neither significantly affects the dependent variable. The analysis therefore, reveals that only gender and marital status significantly influence the dependent variable. Gender has a negative effect, while marital status has a positive effect. Other factors, such as education, age, occupation, type of settlement, and nature of migration, do not appear to have a significant impact on the dependent variable. we conclude therefore that gender and marital status are the only significant

determinants of the challenges faced by migrants in their source regions.

Table 3.14 Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	B	Std. Error
(Constant)	5.050	1.023		4.935	0.000
Gender	-0.439	0.217	-0.230	-2.025	0.046
Marital status	0.214	0.088	0.277	2.428	0.017
Education	-0.048	0.104	-0.048	-0.464	0.644
Age	-0.166	0.118	-0.178	-1.409	0.162
Occupation	0.040	0.063	0.067	0.637	0.526
Type of settlement migrated from	-0.092	0.258	-0.040	-0.355	0.724
Nature of migration	-0.409	0.315	-0.136	-1.300	0.197

Source: Author's Field Work, 2025

3.7 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

1. How does migration affect population composition in Alimosho Local Government Area?

Migration significantly affects the population composition of Alimosho Local Government Area by increasing its ethnic and regional diversity. The data shows that a large portion of residents are from nearby southwestern states like Ogun (18.2%), Oyo (13.1%), and Ondo (9.1%), reflecting regional migration driven by proximity and economic ties (Todaro, 1969; Adepoju, 2000). Past studies have documented Lagos, particularly LGAs like Alimosho, as major recipients of internal migration flow in Nigeria. Alimosho is often characterized as one

of the fastest-growing and most populous LGAs, driven largely by rural-urban migration and economic pull factors (Afolayan, 1998; Ojo, 2018). According to Fadayomi (1996), urban migration often results in the ethnic pluralization of receiving communities, altering their demographic makeup. This is evident in Alimosho, where migrants from southeastern, north-central, and Niger Delta states have a visible, though smaller, presence. These migration patterns change the social and cultural landscape, influence political representation, and shape the demand for housing, education, and services.

2. What are the spatial patterns and characteristics of migration in Alimosho Local Government Area?

Migration into Alimosho Local Government Area (LGA) exhibits clear spatial patterns and characteristics, primarily defined by urban-to-urban movements, long-term settlement, and voluntary relocation. According to the data, a significant majority of migrants (80.8%) moved from other urban areas, while only 19.2% originated from rural settings. This reflects a broader trend in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa, where urban-to-urban migration has become more prominent due to increased urban connectivity and economic opportunities in cities (Potts, 2010; Tacoli, 2007). Additionally, the majority of respondents (77.8%) indicated that they are permanent residents in Alimosho, suggesting that the area is not merely a temporary stop but a destination for long-term settlement. This aligns with Adepoju (2007), who observed that many urban migrants in Nigeria seek stability in emerging suburban areas like Alimosho due to affordable housing and access to livelihoods. Furthermore, the migration in Alimosho is predominantly voluntary, with 88.9% of respondents citing personal reasons for relocating, such as employment, education, and improved living conditions. This high level of agency among migrants supports the findings of Afolayan (1998), who emphasized the role of voluntary migration in urban development across Nigeria.

3. What are the driving factors affecting migration in Alimosho Local Government Area?

Migration to Alimosho Local Government Area is influenced by a combination of strong pull and push factors. The key attracting (pull) factors include job opportunities, which were rated as “Very high” or “High” by most respondents, indicating employment is the strongest motivator for moving to the area. Better housing also ranked highly, suggesting that improved living conditions are a major consideration. Additionally, social networks and urban lifestyle were rated moderately to highly, showing that community connections and city amenities influence settlement decisions (Tacoli, 2007; Afolayan, 1998). The presence of family and friends also emerged as a relevant factor, though with mixed importance across the sample.

On the other hand, push factors from migrants’ areas of origin highlight unemployment and poor living conditions as the most critical reasons for leaving. These issues reflect economic hardship and inadequate infrastructure in many parts of the country (Adepoju, 2007). While insecurity and war were mentioned, they were not significant push factors for most respondents. Other drivers like marriage, job transfers, and family issues played a role for specific individuals but were less universally impactful.

4. What challenges do migrants face in Alimosho Local Government Area?

Migrants in Alimosho LGA face various challenges, particularly in employment, housing, healthcare, and education. While many find job opportunities, 35.4% still report difficulties, reflecting the broader urban employment pressures noted by Adepoju (2007), who highlighted informal labor markets as a barrier for new urban migrants. Although 78.8% do not report poor housing, 21.2% live in substandard conditions—an issue consistent with Afolayan’s (1998) findings on overcrowding and inadequate infrastructure in rapidly urbanizing areas.

Healthcare access remains uneven, with 34.3% of respondents facing difficulties, often due to affordability or service limitations, echoing Tacoli's (2007) observation that urban poor populations struggle with essential services. Most migrants feel safe, with only 7.1% citing security concerns, but 29.3% experience some form of social exclusion. Education access is the most significant challenge, with 58.6% reporting limited access, underlining the persistent inequalities in urban service distribution as discussed by Potts (2010). Overall, over 50% of migrants rated their challenges as moderate to severe, indicating that while Alimosho offers opportunities, integration remains difficult for many, especially in socio-economic terms.

The first hypothesis tests the association between factors attracting migrants to Alimosho. The ANOVA results show a significant relationship ($F = 13.176$, $p = 0.000$). This confirms that factors like job opportunities, housing, and social networks are key motivators for migration to urban areas, consistent with Adepoju (2007) and Afolayan (1998), who highlighted economic and social factors as major drivers of migration.

The second hypothesis, testing the push factors for migration, showed a p-value of 0.053, just above the 0.05 threshold. This suggests no significant association between factors like insecurity and unemployment in pushing migrants from their regions. This finding contrasts with Potts (2010), who noted that economic and environmental challenges are key drivers of migration.

In the third hypothesis, regression analysis found that gender and marital status significantly affect the challenges faced by migrants, with gender negatively and marital status positively impacting the level of challenges. This supports findings from Tacoli (2007), who also noted the importance of social factors in migration experiences. However, the model explained only 13.5% of the variation in challenges, suggesting other factors play a larger role.

CHAPTER FOUR

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This study contains the summary of the discussions from chapter three which examined the assessment of migration and its driving force in Alimosho Local Government Area, Lagos State. It addressed five objectives and three research hypotheses were tested.

The socioeconomic characteristics of migrants in Alimosho Local Government Area reveals a predominantly female population (56.6%) compared to males (43.4%). The majority of respondents are married (46.5%), with singles comprising 32.3% of the sample. Educational attainment is notably high, with 43.4% having tertiary education and 42.4% possessing secondary education, which indicates that migrants are generally well-educated. The age distribution shows that most migrants (40.4%) fall within the 36-45 age bracket, followed by those aged 25-35 (28.3%). Self-employment dominates the occupational structure at 50.5%, followed by civil servants (23.2%). All respondents are citizens of Nigeria, which indicates that internal migration is the primary form of population movement in the area.

The analysis reveals that urban-to-urban migration is the dominant pattern, with 80.8% of migrants originating from urban areas, while only 19.2% migrated from rural areas. This finding challenges the traditional rural-to-urban migration narrative and suggests that inter-urban migration is increasing in Nigeria's migration pattern. Most migrants (77.8%) have established permanent residency, while 22.2% maintain temporary residency. A large volume (88.9%) of movements are voluntary i.e. most migration decisions are driven by personal aspirations rather than forced circumstances – which was a meagre 11.1%. The geographic distribution of migration origins shows Ogun State as the primary source, contributing 35.4%

of all migrants, followed by Oyo State (12.1%) and Imo State (7.1%). This pattern shows the strong migration behaviour between the neighbouring south-western states.

The study investigated the drivers of migration to Alimosho LGA. Job opportunities emerge as the most significant attracting factor, with 54 respondents rating it as "High" or "Very High." Better housing options also serve as a major pull factor, with 47 respondents providing high ratings. Social networks and the presence of family and friends play important but secondary roles in migration decisions. Unemployment is the primary factor pushing people to migrate from their source region, with 50 respondents rating it as "High" or "Very High,". Poor living conditions also significantly influence migration decisions, with 47 respondents providing high ratings. Interestingly, factors such as war and insecurity received low ratings, suggesting that economic rather than security concerns drive most migration in this context.

Despite the opportunities that attract migrants to Alimosho, significant challenges persist. Limited access to education emerges as the most prevalent challenge, affecting 58.6% of respondents. Lack of employment opportunities remains a concern for 35.4% of migrants, while inadequate healthcare access affects 34.3%. Discrimination and social exclusion impact 29.3% of migrants, though security concerns are minimal, affecting only 7.1% of respondents. Most migrants (50.5%) rate their overall challenges as moderate, while 38.4% consider them high or very high, indicating substantial difficulties in integration and livelihood improvement.

Financial assistance or loans are identified as the most crucial support mechanism to improve livelihood, with 42.4% of respondents preferring this intervention. Affordable housing ranks second at 23.2%, followed by access to education and skill development programs at 17.2%. For policy interventions, creating more job opportunities is the top priority (36.4%), followed by enhancing public transportation (17.2%) and developing affordable housing (13.1%).

The ANOVA was used to examine the association between the factors attracting migrants to Alimosho LGA. The hypothesis testing reveals mixed results regarding the relationships between these factors. There is a significant association between factors attracting migrants to Alimosho ($F=13.176$, $p<0.001$), confirming that multiple pull factors work together to influence migration decisions. However, no significant association exists between push factors from source regions ($F=2.640$, $p=0.053$). The relationship between migrants' socioeconomic characteristics and the level of challenges faced shows limited explanatory power ($R^2=0.135$), with only gender and marital status emerging as significant predictors.

4.2 CONCLUSION

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of migration dynamics in Alimosho Local Government Area. The study findings challenge previous understanding of Nigeria's migration pattern. The dominance of urban-to-urban migration over traditional rural-to-urban movement is proof of the evolving nature of internal migration in Nigeria. The study also shows that Alimosho LGA serves as a significant destination for internal migrants, primarily driven by economic opportunities and housing availability.

The research emphasized that while migration to Alimosho offers opportunities for improved livelihoods, migrants face substantial challenges that require targeted interventions. The high educational levels among migrants also suggest a skilled population that can contribute significantly to local economic development, if properly tapped. However, the persistent challenges in education access, employment, and healthcare indicate gaps that must be addressed to maximize the benefits of migration.

The findings highlight the importance of economic factors in driving migration decisions, with unemployment serving as the primary push factor and job opportunities as the main pull factor.

This economic motivation shows 7 the need for policies that create sustainable employment opportunities and support entrepreneurial activities among migrants. The study also reveals the significance of social networks and family connections in migration decisions, though these factors are secondary to economic considerations. The challenges faced by migrants, especially in education access and healthcare, calls to an urgent need for inclusive urban planning that considers the needs of migrant populations.

The findings of this research suggest that with appropriate policies and support systems, migration can be harnessed as a driver of urban development and economic growth in Alimosho Local Government Area.

4.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. The Lagos State Government and Alimosho Local Government should prioritize the creation of diverse employment opportunities. This should include establishing vocational training centers, supporting small and medium enterprises (SMEs), and creating business support programs targeting Entrepreneurs.
2. The government should explore public-private partnerships to develop affordable housing schemes, implement rent control measures, and provide access to housing finance for migrants. This would address both the attraction factor of better housing and the challenge of poor housing conditions faced by some migrants.
3. Since limited access to education affects 58.6% of migrants, representing the highest challenge, immediate intervention is required. This should include building more public schools in high-density migrant areas, implementing scholarship programs for migrant

children, establishing adult education centers for skill upgrading, and ensuring that educational facilities are geographically accessible to migrant communities.

4. With 34.3% of migrants facing inadequate healthcare access, there is a need to expand healthcare infrastructure in Alimosho LGA. This should involve establishing more primary healthcare centers in migrant-dense areas, implementing health insurance schemes accessible to migrants, and training more healthcare personnel.
5. The Government and her Agencies, Private sector and relevant Stakeholders should develop financial support initiatives. This should include microfinance programs, cooperative societies, financial literacy training, and partnerships with commercial banks to provide accessible credit facilities for migrants' businesses.

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